

A NOTE ON TWO SIMILAR TRAMP SPECIES OF
CHONOCEPHALUS WANDOLLECK (DIPT., PHORIDAE)

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The scuttle fly genus *Chonocephalus* Wandolleck was for long in a state of taxonomic confusion because the flightless females and winged males were frequently being treated separately. The result was that the two sexes of the same species were too often being assigned to different species. In order to advance, the known species were reviewed; with the male sex being treated as the primary means of recognition of the species (Disney, 2002). This indicated that only six species were recorded from the Holarctic Region, of which *C. bentacaisei* (Santos Abreu) seemed to be restricted to the Canary Islands. The rest were evidently tramp species transported from other biogeographic regions by man. This paper provided a baseline that allowed the start of a review of the species for the other biogeographic regions. The genus is turning out to be far richer in species than was thought to be the case last century. The Afrotropical species have now been keyed (Disney, 2005) and also the richer fauna of the Neotropical Region (Disney, 2008).

When a single female that closely resembled typical females of *C. depressus* Meijere was reported from Madeira it was tentatively assigned to *C. bentacaisei* (Disney & Aguiar, 2008). However, further material of *C. bentacaisei* allowed recognition that the Afrotropical *C. madagascariensis* Paulian is a synonym of *C. bentacaisei* (Disney, 2009), and it was then recorded from California (Disney & Brown, 2009). So both it and *C. depressus* are evidently tramp species.

We now report two males of *C. depressus* and a further six females from Madeira, with one male and female being procured *in copula*. These females, along with others from other biogeographic regions, indicate that the single female reported from Madeira previously lies within the range of variation for *C. depressus*. These represent the first record of this species for Madeira. The localities and dates for the specimens from Madeira, all of which were collected in Moericke type pan traps, are as follows. 1 ♀, Ariero, São Martinho, Funchal, i.1994; a pair *in copula*, Lugar de Baixo, Ponta do Sol, 9.ix.1992, 304257.58E, 3617819N, 29m (ICLAM-D205) and 1 ♂ and 5 ♀♀, Quebradas, São Martinho, Funchal, 315895.54E, 3613961.32N, 5.vii.2000, 119m (ICLAM-D-315).

Paulian's (1958) description of the female of *C. madagascariensis* does not allow its distinction from that of *C. depressus* and his material has since been lost, so that comparisons of its females with those *C. depressus* have not been possible. Mating pairs or reared series of *C. bentacaisei* are required before its female can be properly characterised. The presence of *C. bentacaisei* in the Canary Islands has been recently confirmed (Disney *et al.*, 2010).

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